

D5.2 (M12) - Report of recommended implementation strategy for FAIR sharing of human data

(an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

Project duration: 2022-04-01 - 2026-03-31 (48 months)

Funder: The Research Council of Norway

Project number: [322392](#)

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Publication date: 2024-02-26

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.1069552](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1069552)

Keywords: Data Management; Metadata; Data submission, annotation, and curation; Sensitive data

Context

This report provides an update on the work of Task 5.2 of WP5. The scope of this task is to facilitate the creation and sharing of data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) by aligning with national and international stakeholders. This document describes the metadata models available and analyses their strengths and weaknesses. The reports finally provide some recommendations for the Norwegian node of the Federated Genome-phenome Archive.

As stated in the FAIR data principles¹, FAIR-oriented sharing of data requires alignment with community practices. ELIXIR Norway benefits from being part of a dense network of relevant organisations and infrastructures. Some of these are directly related to ELIXIR Europe², such as the Federated Human Data³ and Research Data Management⁴ ELIXIR communities, while others are external organisations such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)⁵. ELIXIR Norway is also participating in relevant activities promoted by the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC)⁶ such as the HEILSA project⁷ and in European activities such as the European Genome Data Infrastructure (GDI)⁸, the

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/>

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/human-data>

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management>

⁵ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

⁶ <https://neic.no/>

⁷ <https://neic.no/heilsa/>

⁸ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG)⁹ project, EOSC4Cancer¹⁰, and EOSC Entrust¹¹. At the same time, the activity of this task is also to align with national stakeholders including hospitals and biobanks and associated infrastructures such as Biobank Norway¹².

Delivery

As obvious from the large number of stakeholders or related organisations and projects, a large chunk of the activities of this task is represented by meetings of various kinds. In regards to the implementation of the FAIR data principles, the metadata working group (WG) of the Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive (FEGA) is particularly relevant. This group collects a number of metadata experts working in the field of human data and its scope is to facilitate the creation of a rich and FAIR-oriented metadata solution to be adopted at the European level, a scope which is very much in line with the activities of the task being reported here. Members of this task participate actively in the meetings of this group to help define the model. As part of this activity, a task member also participated in a survey from the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI)¹³ to assess the national needs and considerations for defining a better model. Note that the technical implementation of the said metadata model is a direct follow-up of this activity and it is planned to be carried out as part of ELIXIR₃ in D5.4 where members of T5.2 are also involved.

Outcomes

There are multiple beneficiaries of this work and of its possible future implementations as the European landscape of GDPR-compliant federated data infrastructures evolves. A well-described and unified metadata model at the European level facilitates sharing and discovering data and automating the submission and retrieval processes. This enables the researchers and data producers (e.g. genomics core facilities) to make their data discoverable and programmers to develop tools to handle this type of data without incurring interoperability issues. The usage of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) enables GDPR compliance and standardises the process of sharing. At the same time, it also enables reproducibility in the data analysis by the development of libraries and environments that are compatible with the data independently from the TRE of choice.

Based on the task outcomes, the recommendations collected here should be developed when mature enough, and a system for assessing the continuously evolving state-of-the-art of FAIR data sharing should be in place. Researchers and data producers should be encouraged at an early stage to compile a FAIR-compliant metadata form to facilitate the streamlining of data in the federated infrastructure.

⁹ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

¹¹ <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-entrust/>

¹² <https://bbmri.no/>

¹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

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Metadata Models

In this section, we describe the main features of the metadata models in use on federated nodes of the EGA. Recommendations for the Norwegian national node of the Federated Genome-phenome Archive¹⁴ are provided together with other more general considerations.

The Central EGA Metadata Model

This is the “traditional” metadata model currently used on EGA. It is sometimes referred to as the Central EGA (CEGA) metadata model and it is developed by EBI and made available on their GitHub repository¹⁵. Metadata according to this mode is required to be submitted together with the data files to successfully upload material on the EGA archive. The metadata fields aim to describe the details of the experiment (e.g. the sequencing technology) and to define the relationships between the various objects (e.g. between experiments and samples).

Both the metadata schema and the associated submission procedures change depending on the type of data submitted. While details of the submission are not relevant to the scope of this document, as the data upload will occur at the federate nodes and not on the central repository, the metadata architecture is relevant. CEGA has adopted the metadata schemas from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)¹⁶, also known as ENA checklists¹⁷, and expanded them to include additional objects such as *Policy*, *Dataset*, and *DAC* (Data Access Committee), relevant to sensitive human data. As a result, the complete metadata schema comprises 9 objects: *Study*, *Sample*, *Experiment*, *Analysis*, *Run*, *DAC*, *Policy*, *Dataset*, and *Submission*. A more detailed description of these objects is available in a table on the dedicated webpage¹⁸. It is important to note that the standard is represented using both the Extensible Markup Language (XML) Schema Definition (XSD) and JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) formats, the latter being a more recent development of the schema which is becoming increasingly relevant over time, as it will be clarified later in this document. Besides the standards defined in the schemas, EGA inherits from ENA the Sample checklists.

¹⁴ <https://ega.elixir.no/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/EbiEga/ega-metadata-schema>

¹⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

¹⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

¹⁸ <https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/ega-schema/>

The new central EGA Metadata Model

There is a new metadata model currently in development at EBI. When this model enters the production stage, it will replace the existing one, although backwards compatibility will be ensured. This model moves away from the checklists inherited from ENA and aims at improving the FAIRness of the standard by requesting a larger amount of ontology classes and by performing systematic validation of the entries beyond standard JSON schema validation. This model is distributed as a set of JSON schemas, available in a dedicated folder of the GitHub repository¹⁹. The approach towards the validation of metadata objects against these schemas is through the ELIXIR biovalidator²⁰, a JSON Schema validator extended from the javascript library AJV²¹. The biovalidator covers many validation use cases related to the life sciences, including ontology and taxonomy validation. Ontology-related operations are performed via calls to the Application Programming Interface (API) of the Ontology Lookup Service²² (OLS), a repository for biomedical ontologies that aims to provide a single point of access to the latest ontology versions. Validation of taxonomies is performed through calls to the dedicated ENA API²³.

The full list of ontologies recommended in the CEQA model is:

- The National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT)²⁴
- The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)²⁵
- The Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO)²⁶
- The Uber-anatomy Ontology (UBERON)²⁷
- The Sequence Ontology (SO)²⁸
- International Classification of Diseases (ICD)²⁹
- GENO ontology³⁰
- The ontology of bioscientific data analysis and data management (EDAM)³¹

¹⁹ <https://github.com/EbiEga/ega-metadata-schema/tree/main/schemas>

²⁰ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

²¹ <https://ajv.js.org/>

²² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4>

²³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/swagger-ui/index.html>

²⁴ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/NCIT>

²⁵ <https://hpo.jax.org/app/>

²⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>

²⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon>

²⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/so>

²⁹ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ICD10>

³⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/geno>

³¹ <https://edamontology.org/page>

- The Data Use Ontology (DUO)³²
- The Cell Ontology (CL)³³
- The SemanticScience Integrated Ontology (SIO)³⁴
- The Ontology for MIRNA target (OMIT)³⁵
- The Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI)³⁶
- The Mondo Disease Ontology (MONDO)³⁷
- The Gender, Sex and Sexual Orientation Ontology (GSSO)³⁸
- The Genetic Epidemiology Ontology (GENEPIO)³⁹
- The BRENDA Tissue Ontology (BTO)⁴⁰
- The Phenotype and Trait Ontology (PATO)⁴¹
- The Medical Action Ontology (MAXO)⁴²

Of particular relevance is the use of DUO codes to define the data use conditions of all the data present on EGA. DUO codes allow EGA to semantically tag datasets with restrictions about their usage, making them discoverable automatically based on the authorisation level of users or intended usage. Users are asked to identify DUO codes as part of the submission process which reflects how the data can be used based on participant consent forms. More details can be found on the dedicated webpage⁴³.

GHGA Metadata Schema

The German Human Genome-phenome Archive (GHGA)⁴⁴ is a national data infrastructure for highly sensitive human omics and health data operating under a coherent ethical-legal framework. GHGA promotes data exchange and secondary uses of research and clinical data. As part of this effort, it serves as the German node of FEGA, maintaining thus compliance with national data privacy and protection regulations while, at the same time, coordinating with global infrastructures and initiatives for data sharing. As part of the effort to make the data FAIR, a GHGA *Metadata Workstream* has developed the GHGA Metadata Schema and associated documentation, reported in a white paper⁴⁵ shared on Zenodo.

³² <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/duo.html>

³³ <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/cl.html>

³⁴ <https://jbiomedsem.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/2041-1480-5-14>

³⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/omit>

³⁶ <https://obi-ontology.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/mondo>

³⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/gssso>

³⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/genepio>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/bto>

⁴¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/pato>

⁴² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/maxo>

⁴³ <https://web2.ega-archive.org/data-use-conditions>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ghga.de>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8341224>

The GHGA metadata schemas expand on the original EGA/ENA model to better represent the granularity of metadata from specific communities with an initial focus on cancer and rare disease data. The architecture of the schema allows for further extensions and developments while maintaining a stable core which remains CEGA-compatible, the latter being a requirement for being a node of the federated infrastructure. In addition to the metadata objects in the CEGA model (described in this deliverable in the dedicated section), the GHGA schema contains three additional entities, namely *Publication*, *Condition* and *Trio*. On top of these additional objects, the GHGA model reorganises all the relevant entities into a novel set of higher-level objects called *modules*. Seven of these *modules* comprise the whole model: *Basic*, *Sample*, *Sequencing*, *Phenotype*, *Data Use Conditions*, *Dataset*, and *Analysis*. The Figure below, taken from the white paper presenting the GHGA model⁴⁶ and distributed under *Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International*, offers a graphical representation of the *modules*, their subcategories (matching the respective objects from the CEGA model such as *Study* or *Sample*) and the relations between them. All these properties fall into three categories *Required*, *Recommended*, and *Optional*.

Figure 1: An overview of the GHGA Metadata Schema v1.0. Entities in the schema (white boxes) are grouped into seven modules depending on the type of information they represent (e.g. sequencing data, sample data, phenotype data). Entities and therefore the modules are connected to each other, except for *Analysis*, *Dataset* and *Data Use Conditions Module*. The modules are highlighted in different colors. Modules can be grouped together to enable different kinds of submissions, depending on the data the data submitter is able to submit to GHGA.

⁴⁶ Iyappan, A., et al. Metadata Schema for the German Human Genome-phenome Archive. 1, Zenodo, 13 Sept. 2023, doi:10.5281/zenodo.8341224.

As in the case of the most recent version of the CEGA model, metadata entries are regulated by controlled vocabularies and ontologies. Most of the ontologies previously listed here for the CEGA model are also used in the GHGA model. On top of these, some additional ones are utilised:

- The Human Ancestry Ontology (HANCESTRO)⁴⁷
- The Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO)⁴⁸
- SNOMED clinical terms (SNOMED CT)⁴⁹

Ontologies that are used on the CEGA model but not here are the previously defined SO, PATO, MAXO, and GENO. These are however mappable to standards in GHGA.

In regards to compatibility with other common standards in the community, the GHGA model is fully compatible with the popular Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment (MIAME)⁵⁰, Minimal Information about a high throughput SEQuencing Experiment (MINSEQE)⁵¹ and Minimum Information about a Single-Cell Experiment (minSCE)⁵² implemented e.g. on ArrayExpress⁵³. On top of these, compatibility with the EGA (and, thus, the ENA model) ensures in most cases also compliance with the Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS)⁵⁴.

The metadata model is available in Yet Another Markup Language (YAML) format at the dedicated GitHub repository⁵⁵. GHGA uses the linkML framework⁵⁶ for autogenerating from the aforementioned YAML sources many technology-specific artefacts such as JSON schemas, Python Dataclasses, Pydantic⁵⁷ models, Resource Description Framework (RDF)⁵⁸, and W3C Web Ontology Language (OWL)⁵⁹. This enables multiple strategies for machine-actionable collection of metadata and promotes the interoperability of the model. The model is also provided as spreadsheets⁶⁰ if a more manual approach for metadata collection is desired.

⁴⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/hancestro>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/ordo>

⁴⁹ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/SNOMEDCT>

⁵⁰ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.32b10v>

⁵¹ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.a55z32>

⁵² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9302581/>

⁵³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

⁵⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.32b10v>

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/ghga-de/ghga-metadata-schema/tree/main/src/schema>

⁵⁶ <https://github.com/ghga-de/ghga-metadata-schema/tree/main/src/schema>

⁵⁷ <https://docs.pydantic.dev/latest/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

⁶⁰ <https://github.com/ghga-de/ghga-metadata-schema/tree/main/spreadsheets>

Recommendations

It is not straightforward to come up with a comprehensive set of recommendations at this stage, as on one side the technology behind the schemas is evolving together with the models and, on the other, FEAGA has not been active long enough to capture the requirements of all the possible users, both national and international. However, both the new CEAGA and the GHGA model have strengths that make them much more FAIR-oriented than the model currently adopted by the Norwegian FEAGA node (i.e. the CEAGA model). The current CEAGA model should, however, not be entirely disregarded in future developments due to its compatibility with the ENA checklists and, thus, with the available tooling e.g. for the systematic upload of large quantities of data, sometimes referred to as *data brokering*⁶¹, which is currently being addressed by both the ELIXIR RDM Community⁶² and the ELIXIR Data Platform⁶³. Some of these efforts are centred around a specific abstract model called Investigation, Study, Assay (ISA), its representation as JSON schemas (ISA-JSON)⁶⁴, and the associated ISA framework⁶⁵. We believe general interoperability across EGA-related metadata formats and ISA-related ones would be beneficial to the general interoperability and reusability of the deposited data. This should be addressed, however, at a European level and it is, thus, not a recommendation for the Norwegian national node.

Another consideration to be addressed at the international/European level is the apparent lack of a recommendation for a metadata management tool implementing the aforementioned metadata models. While both FEAGA and GHGA offer several formats, it is unclear which path would allow for a more complete and less prone to human error metadata collection. While spreadsheets are likely to be the preferred way of working for experimentalists, they can be time-consuming to fill out and do not natively offer support for ontologies. One solution to the latter could be the usage of a tool such as Rightfield⁶⁶, which, to the knowledge of the authors, is not taken into consideration by the groups developing the metadata models. Other tools, such as FAIRDOME SEEK⁶⁷, should be considered both by data producers and EGA-service providers to make the collection of metadata more systematic. There is ongoing work to make SEEK ISA-compatible⁶⁸, so its adoption could address also the consideration in the previous paragraph. However, this is not a final recommendation, as FAIRDOME SEEK requires extensive setup from a proficient data steward before adoption and because the graphic interface has been reported to be

⁶¹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_brokering

⁶² <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management>

⁶³ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data>

⁶⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.yhLgTV>

⁶⁵ <https://isa-tools.org/index.html>

⁶⁶ <https://fair-dom.org/rightfield>

⁶⁷ <https://seek4science.org/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.elixir-belgium.org/services/DataHub>

not intuitive enough. Improvement in the tool or newer implementation of similar models could be game changers for curating (meta)data.

When it comes to the selection of the metadata model to be adopted by the Norwegian node, the recommendation is to align with the CEGA model and follow its development. This is based on the fact that there is an ongoing dialogue between the CEGA and the GHGA metadata groups to capture the best practices into a possibly unique solution allowing, at the same time, for customisations and extensions. This has the potential to create a model that benefits from the strength of both models, including

- Compatibility with ENA and the MIxS format [CEGA; GHGA]
- Compatibility with the MIAME, MINSEQE, MINSCE models and related repositories (e.g. ArrayExpress) [GHGA]
- Consistent validation of ontology terms via a dedicated tool (biovalidator) [CEGA]
- Possibility of moving automatically the model into multiple formats and of creating Python classes with internal validation through LinkML [GHGA]
- A granular selection of ontology classes [GHGA; CEGA]

Conclusions

There are currently three viable metadata models for FEGA submissions. The older one is not FAIR-oriented but benefits from compatibility with similar objects in the ELIXIR ecosystem and might be easier to implement in existing tools. The other two models (one of which is currently not in production yet) exhibit much higher adherence to the FAIR principles. One of the two exhibits better interoperability than the other (the GHGA model), while the other (CEGA) comes with better tooling for validation. As these models follow the same core metadata structure, merging could be possible and would strengthen the overall concept of a federated repository and the way it enables the FAIR Data principles. Some hindrances in the adoption of these models are represented by a lack of tooling for metadata collection and curation. A management system where the models themselves are implemented with all the required controlled terminology and internal validation would be extremely beneficial in promoting the FAIR sharing of data. The Norwegian node is not recommended to build a new metadata model, but rather to contribute to the development of a unified and more FAIR-oriented model via participation at dedicated meetings and other events.